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TEACHING DECISION MAKING IN ARCHITECTURE STUDIO COURSES USING A NEW TECHNOLOGICAL CASE-BASED TOOL

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ABSTRACT

Design fixation is an effect that prevents designers from producing creative solutions. This document presents an experiment carried out at a studio course which demonstrates the existence of high rates of fixation among Architecture students, where decision making while designing is characterized by the transposition of typified components from referenced cases. As a consequence a Case-Based Design Aid (CBDA) is formulated to support design processes by enabling students to visualize similar problems to those presented in studio courses which have been solved by professionals in real practices. The strategy is to relate the technical data of cases to their real contexts and to the situations that produced them into acyclic graphs. The final objective is to increase students' analysis, design, and creativity capacities by referencing precedent practices.

Keywords: Design fixation, Case-Based Design Aid, Acyclic graphs.

INTRODUCTION

This paper presents an experiment conducted among Architecture students from 2nd and 3^{er}d year in the University of Los Andes (Uniandes) which aims to verify the existence of design fixation patterns. In response to the obtained results a technological Case-Based tool to support Case-based Design (CBD) processes is also presented.

In architectural design domain educators comment the difficulties that result from prematurely committing to a design solution seen in a referenced case, as it is difficult for students to get away from that idea and to produce creative solutions (Purcell & Gero, 1996; Heylighen, 2000).

On one hand, copying functional arrangements and characteristics from known cases is known in problem solving as *design fixation*. Its existence has been proved in other fields but in Architecture where data is insufficient. Some of these experiments were conducted by Jansson & Smith (1991). In their experiments students and professional mechanical engineers were asked to design a bicycle rack for cars, a measuring cup for blind people and a machine to take samples and measure speed and pressure in the intestinal tracks using given examples. The results for design fixation in these experiments were positive.

On the other hand, creativity in a design solution deals with knowing previous cases and "*giving a new order to existing components*" (Watson & Perera, 1997). Maher & Gero (1993) define a creative design as the "*formation of new specifications for a new situation*". Then, creativity has to do both with knowing past experiences from similar cases and the ability to create new functional orders in a presented context. From these two definitions it can be argued that creativity can be seen as an opposite effect to design fixation patterns.

DESIGN FIXATION IN ARCHITECTURE

In Architectural design domain and other domains Gero and Purcell (1996) have conducted quantitative studies verifying fixation patterns and detected that design fixation within Architecture students is related to the level of familiarity the designer possesses with the referenced case or cases. However, in their experiment with Architects only a small sample presented fixation, so it is insufficient data to conclude that fixation patterns do exist in Architecture students. Heylighen (2000) repeated an

experiment on the discussed topic without taking into account the issue of familiarity of cases. In this experiment students were asked to design a hall entrance for an apartment building with provided cases, so students were not free to choose cases they liked or felt familiar with. As a consequence no effect of fixation was observed.

However, another research held by the Final Project Committee at the ETSAB University in Barcelona showed high fixation rates in students that presented their final project. These are some of their conclusion (Casals, 2005):

- Most of the presented projects copied visual models taken from fashion magazines. This source of knowledge might be called typified knowledge.
- Many of the components did not have a justification despite being correctly calculated.

Philosopher John Silber (2007) also refers to this notion in professional Architects from modernity and post-modernity to contemporary practices. Professional architects also tend to be fixated on concepts and components that Silber has called *absurd*, because fixation may produce functional inconsistencies that remain in the new design (Purcell, 1996; Silber, 2007) although this absurdism is not the topic of this paper.

One of the exposed fixated cases showed by Silber is Frank Lloyd Wright's Kauffman House. Wright's fixation on slender cantilever elements that Mr. Kauffman's consultants detected in the early design were built and deformed excessively. These elements were strengthened after the project was completed (Silber, 2007).

Another fixation example on professional designers is Frank Gehry's Walt Disney Concert Hall. Its curved metallic façade has been repetitively placed in other projects such the Bilbao Museum. At the Walt Disney Concert Hall its façades produced annoying and undesired glares to neighbors, so it had to be sandblasted after several different solutions were tested (Schiler, 2005).

Theoretically design fixation patterns can occur in the resolution of a new design both at a concept or component level. Concepts are the general way of understanding a problem so objects can be spatially and functionally configured (Jansson & Smith, 1991; Heylighen, 2000), while components refer to those particular built systems with characteristics such as color, geometry, mechanical properties, construction processes, etc. (Heylighen, 2000). Fixation on components may derive from observed cases or analogies from other objects as it will be observed in the experiment conducted in Architecture students in the University of Los Andes (Uniandes).

EXPERIMENT: DESIGN FIXATION IN ARCHITECTURE STUDENTS

The presented experiment was conducted to establish whether design fixation on cases does exist in students at the Architecture Department in Uniandes, and to establish how creative students are when designing a new building. These items were measured during a real pedagogical design exercise at a schematic stage in the *tectonic studio course*¹.

The evaluated exercise is done every semester and it consists of designing a hybrid building with health services, administration and sports facilities. The latter claims the resolution of one or more buildings to contain swimming pools and sport fields in one or various large span buildings where design fixation and creativity were measured.

SUBJECTS

The study was conducted among eighteen students organized into nine pairs from a total population of forty students.

METHODOLOGY

Students were given the basic program and a set location to develop the architectural scheme. They were given a week to design and prepare their oral presentation.

¹ The *Tectonic studio course* belongs to the projects area and the formative cycle in the Department of Architecture at the University of Los Andes in Bogota. It contains students from 2nd and 3rd year.

During the exercise students were not given instructions about the experiment being held to stimulate a real pedagogical exercise to be done. In this manner students were free to use or not existing cases they liked.

After the oral presentation of each project was done students were asked what design aid they used to solve the large span structure, and if referenced cases was the answer they were asked which one they observed the most, and what type of information was contained in the documents they consulted. These collected data would allow establishing what design aid is used the most by these students and verifying design fixation and creativity patterns among groups which use aids that allow these measurements to be done.

Verification of results on design fixation was made on three basic structural characteristics: materials, form, and structural system. On one hand, fixation was verified by the comparison of student's new projects and the referenced case each group claimed to have used the most as a design support method. To establish fixation rates similar characteristics were given a scale ranging from one to three points where one is null fixation and three is the maximum, so an average percentage of design fixation patterns for each group and for the general group could be set. On the other hand, creativity was measured by the not fixated rates according to the given definitions, as this rate correspond to different solutions from the observed ones.

RESULTS

The results showed that 76% of the nine groups used at least one case contained primarily in photos, drawings (or plans) and descriptions in magazines and internet, 12% did not use a reference case but various theory books, and finally 12% used analogies such "cranes placed one next to another" (figure 1). Thus, the study focuses on eight groups that used design support methods such as cases and analogies from other objects which allowed direct verification of design fixation patterns.

Figure 1. Design support methods used by students during the design exercise.

Within these eight groups, the results shown in figure 2 demonstrate that two groups (G.2 and G.8) which correspond to a 25% of the eight groups transcribed every evaluated structural characteristic, while every group had more or less fixated characteristics ranging from 33% to 100%. In general terms fixation on materials scored 81%, fixation on structural system scored 75%, while fixation on form scored 38%. From this point of view form is the characteristic that students vary the most.

As a result, the general fixation rate within the eight groups that used cases and analogies in the evaluated designs was 65%, while the other 35% correspond to different answers to those seen in the referenced cases, which can be qualified as creative solutions as they are different from the referenced ones (figure 3). In general terms, design fixation on components is positioned above creativity. Thus, it is clear that design methods such typified knowledge contained in photos, drawings and plans used by students provoke high rates of fixation and do not manage to encourage students to design different and creative solutions.

Figure 2. Design fixation of groups that used cases and analogies.

Figure 3. General design fixation and creativity rates.

The most creative solution was designed by group 5 (figure 4). This group consulted a space grid structure placed in a vault form. The new schematic design was a space grid structure with the same materials but conforming frames which were complemented with a two-dimensional grid to make a lighter and cheaper structure. Its fixation rate was 33%, which shows that design fixation does always exist in the subjects evaluated; however, some groups and designs present more creativity than others.

Figure 4. Model of group 5. The most creative solution which shows a space grid structure in steel conforming frames complemented with two a dimensional grid. This was designed using a case with a spatial grid structure with a vault form.

To sum up, referencing similar cases is the design aid students from the selected course use the most and they become fixated in different levels at least on a single referenced case or object when designing a new building. The used design support methods can be characterized as graphic catalogues of existing solutions for a presented problem.

DISCUSSION

Design fixation was verified in architecture students from the selected studio course. Its effect hinders

creativity and also prevents students from the proposition of new solutions.

According to theory decision-making processes are theoretically characterized by the conscious comparison between contextualized alternatives so new solutions can be proposed in a different context (Dillon, 1998). Thus, decision-making in evaluated students is minimal if compared to fixation rates, and is null in two of the evaluated groups.

The hypothesis from obtained results is that design fixation is directly caused by tools that do not encourage a conscious decision-making process while designing. This raises the need of new design support tools that manage to increase student's analysis and design abilities.

EXPLANATORY CASE STUDIES AS A STRATEGY TO SUPPORT DECISION-MAKING PROCESSES IN PROJECTS

To propose a design support aid it is necessary to establish what the used methods for acquiring new knowledge are used by students and professional within architectural design domain. On one hand, a design task involves two general types of knowledge which correspond to the general forms of fixation: concept and component knowledge. On the other hand, the commonly used methods shown in table 1 are heuristics, metaphors, analogies, typified knowledge, and case studies (Heylighen, 2000).

The case study method is different to typified cases, and it is the most efficient method as it highly feeds both concept and component knowledge. Typified knowledge commonly used by students while designing feeds component knowledge and hinders the understanding of key facts of a design so the increasing of design analysis and design capacities is not achieved. This is why a transition from typified support methods to tools that integrally train students in both conceptual and component knowledge is needed.

METHOD	Component Knowledge	Concept Knowledge
-Heuristics	High	Low
-Analogies	High	Medium
-Metaphors	Low	High
-Types	High	Low
-Case studies	High	High

Table 1. Design support methods in architectural design and types of knowledge they are likely to supply. Heylighen, Ann. 2000.

There are many types of case studies. According to Robert Yin (1988) when conducting a research cases can be classified as *explanatory, descriptive or exploratory*. The first one tries to explain why a phenomenon happened, the second one describes a phenomenon just like types do, and the third one is used to prove a theory. In this order, explanatory case studies can reveal why a particular design with its characteristics happened, rather than giving typified data to students to be fixated on, reason why these types of case studies can be used to transmit design decision-making processes from real projects to students rather than just typified data.

CASE STUDIES AND CASE-BASED DESIGN

In 1919 a separate faculty of Business Administration within Harvard University realized the lack of appropriate methods to approach the complexity of the profession (Spangler, 1984). As a consequence new methods were needed to potentiate creativity and logic in problem solving in students. This is how the case study method was born as a strategy for bringing real documented experiences to students (Spangler 1984).

Case studies rely on the principle of being capable of teaching both theory and experience at the same time. This is fully compatible with the way architects learn particular concepts and components (Heylighen, 2000).

This learning support method is attractive for many disciplines because it has the capacity to unravel causal links or “war stories” within a single or

multiple case studies (Spangler, 1984; Groat ,2002). However, when cases are studied it should be taken into account that there is not a right answer or solution but different approaches which aim to teach students to think in context and to develop analysis, synthesis, critical thinking, decision making and values such as innovation and creativity (Monterrey Institute of Technology and Higher Education s.f.; Watson & Perera, 1997)

In the design domain a Case-Based Design (CBD) is the product of the interaction between known cases, a particular context of a presented problem, and the particular domain knowledge as it is shown in figure 5 (Watson & Perera, 1997). Thus, a CBD process depends on the number of cases stored in the brain of the designer or a technological tool. These items integrate to solve a problem and to generate a new solution through the understanding of situations of studied cases which allows modifying past solutions.

Figure 5. The framework for Case-Based Design (CBD).

In this manner, the CBD model directly enhances creativity as it indexes to the dynamic memory of the designer a number of objects and knowledge from past cases and allows inferences to be done, finding similarities and developing an inductive and heuristic reasoning. This model can assist a design process by the creation of systems that contain multiple designers’ knowledge (Heylighen, 2000).

Another alternative to solve the detected problem would be the direct observation by students of the dynamics of real architecture offices. However, professional practices in Architecture offices at Uniandes are optional and only occur in advanced semesters. In this way, the most viable option to bring precedent real design practices to students is

to structure and store them into a technological Case-Based Design Aid (CBDA)

THE CASE-BASED DESIGN AID

The main parts of a CBDA are the knowledge structure and organization, the recovery and adaptation or manipulation processes, and how the system learns or grows (Neuckermans & Heylighen, 2000).

There are many case-based systems created to support new designs. These existing systems within the architectural design domain have two basic orientations. The first ones are those like *Archie II* and *Precedents* where knowledge is structured in different sections (mainly concepts and components) to be searched by users. The adaptation of the case must be done by the user as these systems are basically designed for students who have the responsibility to understand, implement or ignore the information presented.

The second and most common types of CBDA are those such as CADRE, FABEL, IDIOM, SEED o CBArch which structure knowledge to find similar cases that are automatically or semi automatically adapted by intelligent systems which force the existing retrieved case to fit a new context using mainly dimensional and topological adaptations (Cavieres, 2011). As a result, a similar functioning fixated case is produced.

The particular orientations of existing CBDA range from a variety of topics such as spaces, structural design or specialized mechanical systems. However, whether architecture is an ill-structured domain (Watson & Perera, 1997; Neuckermans, 2000) it is not accurate to synthesize its particular knowledge into a pre-established model, so existing systems that attempt to organize knowledge are inadequate for teaching.

Thus, given the impossibility to organize knowledge in an initial model to attach cases, the new CBDA exposed in this paper mainly focuses on showing contextualized knowledge in design processes as they truly happened with its evaluated alternatives during every stage of the process, so the variables that were part of the final resolution can be clearly

pointed out and taken into account by the students, instead of focusing on completed projects that existing CBDA are full of.

Behind every great piece of Architecture there is a mental effort that gives life to architectural form...

*Carlos Martí Arís. La cimbra y el Arco, p 10.
(Translated by the authors).*

In response to these facts, a new CBDA tool called *Situational Knowledge Objects of Construction* (SKOC) was designed and is currently under development. It is an authoring tool for an existing web-based repository system of *Knowledge Objects of Construction* (KOC). SKOC uses dynamic situations to transmit design processes to students, as situations and its definitions are the main input for human decision-making and they depict chained and related events that result from human interpretation of problems (Moro, 2009).

THE KOC SYSTEM

KOC is a repository of component knowledge of buildings and construction with an ontological structure (ArCo) that allows indexing spatial and constructive components, processes or activities, materials and functionalities during any stage of the lifecycle of a building.

It was designed for two main applications. Its main function is to serve as an online library to conserve constructive practices. Knowledge in temporary organizations of construction and design firms tend to be lost as a result of the dispersion of teams after each project is executed. It has attracted interest from private companies. The second function of KOC is its application as a learning tool for Architecture students in technical courses, given operative difficulties to organize visits to real building projects (Villazon, 2010).

A Knowledge Object is a piece of graphic or textual information (i.e. pictures, videos, drawings, plans, documents, etc.) that describes objects during a design, construction, use or deconstruction phase of a building, such a concrete beam, its particular formwork, its cast and vibration process, etc. (figure

6) . These objects are stored and semantically organized using *ArCo* (Villazon, 2010).

Figure 6. Example of a Knowledge Object. The façade of the Telefonica office building case study.

THE SKOC AUTHORIZING TOOL²

The framework of SKOC is divided into three general parts (figure 7). The first one is the knowledge structure which uses graphs with situations, an index, an ontology, and KOs. The second one is the case retrieval (search and explorer). And the third one is its growth strategy. Just as in *Archie II* and in *Precedents* the final adaptation of cases is omitted and must be performed by the student using graphical tools such as CAD drawings, models, etc.

Despite SKOC is also intended to show KOs to students, it mainly focuses on the held design process that has led to the physical resolution, construction, or deconstructions of structural, mechanical, exterior or interior enclosure systems. For this reason, qualitative and explanatory case studies on presented problems in class should be done. The main objective of this CBDA is to allow students to easily visualize a precedent case that teachers consider of best practice within a problem. According to theory, after studying cases students will increase their synthesis, analysis and design capacities to finally overcome the dominant design fixation patterns observed. In this manner, to an existing typified knowledge repository system a new case-based tool is added.

Figure 7. The framework of SKOC.

² SKOC is available for public although some functions require a username and password. The website is: <http://157.253.201.47:8080/KOC/caso/listar.htm>

CREATING A CASE FOR SKOC

Creating a case for SKOC has two main stages. The first one is the formulation of the case study and the second one is its uploading.

The research and formulation of the case is made by an assigned investigator. Every explanatory case study should use primary sources as a base, such as consulting documents, interviews with designers and owners, guided tours, etc. in order to gain credibility (Martínez, 2006; Yin, 1988). From the developed case individual KOs such as plans, consulting information, constructive processes, etc. are extracted depending on the problem that is being dealt with and the real situations presented.

Consequently, the large written documents that have been produced at the previous stage must be fragmented into situations and KOs to be included in SKOC. There is an annotator who loads simple objects and attach them to the existing ontology to create KOs, and a different one who loads cases as *dynamic situations* of the particular case. The annotator of cases also links situation to already loaded knowledge objects.

KNOWLEDGE STRUCTURE

Each case is structured in a case uploader in a *directed acyclic graph* which uses two basic components: nodes called situations and arrows representing causal or functional coordinated relations among situations (figure 9).

Graphs are a traditionally used strategy to model and understand complex problems and realities with its implicit knowledge so it is being used in this tool. Complex phenomena such architectural design are not easily apprehended by other means, reason why graphs are widely applied in the proposition of robotic systems, social sciences, natural sciences, etc (Coriat 1989).

In the case uploader platform each situation is loaded by the researcher (figure 8), defined and summarized as written information defined by the following components (Villate, 2010):

- One or more objectives, problems or answers a single situation must fulfill.
- A justification explaining why the current situation is reached from a previous situation as a result of a decision making process.
- A set of alternatives for the resolution of the set objectives which can be real or hypothetical and can be linked to particular existing or new KOs. These alternatives are sometimes contained under various topics, as a single situation may lead to a variety of new situations.
- A set of KOs and links to other knowledge objects contained in ArCo which describe a situation and its alternatives.

The screenshot shows a web form for uploading a situation. The title is "Situación". There are several input fields and a text area. The "Nombre" field contains "Iluminación directa indeseable.". The "Descripción adicional" field contains a text box with the following text: "La inapropiada localización en sentido norte-sur del edificio preexistente para el nuevo uso, implica la continua incidencia de la radiación solar en las fachadas acristaladas más extensas, en oriente y occidente, lo que ante una inadecuada ventilación genera una acción de efecto invernadero, y por ende, temperaturas por encima de la zona de confort térmico que deben situarse entre los 18 y 25 ° C." Below the text area is a rating scale from "Deficiente" to "Sobresaliente" with "INTERMEDIO" selected. There are buttons for "Alternativas", "Pregunta", "Adicionar Nueva Alternativa", and "Adicionar Nueva ???objetivo???".

Figure 8. A situation being uploaded in SKOC.

There is also an index of loaded cases with its technical sheet that contains the main problems every case has been designed for, the main concepts the problem was thought with by the real actors, and data such as architects, year and function. Concepts are determined by the investigator after the case is made and may be located at any stage of the general graph. These problems and concepts are to be included when new cases are loaded.

One of the cases already loaded is the Telefonica office building in Bogota (figures 9 and 10). This case has been designed as an explanatory case applied to a particular exercise in the *tectonic* studio course. The essential dealt problem is the reuse of an existing structure for the implementation of a new

use. This case attaches key concepts such as bioclimatic conditioning, energy efficiency, natural ventilation and structural complementation among others. These concepts are discussed every semester during the development of the new designs in the studio and help setting particular KOC orders to components.

RETRIEVAL AND APLICATIONS

SKOC can be used in two basic ways to fit two types of commonly used case studies in pedagogy according to the Monterrey Institute of Technology and Higher Education: for students to search similar cases, and for teachers to promote discussions in a collaborative environment within the studio class.

engine where the problem is typed and the most similar loaded cases are retrieved. The user can also filter his findings per year, architects or function. A second possibility for students is to search by concepts.

Then, the user can access the case explorer platform of graphs. Students may explore and abstract graph (synthesized graphs with few nodes and no alternatives which describe the general held process), or the whole graph incrementally from initial to final situations, so they do not focus directly on the resolution of the building but on the process.

However, if a student searches a concept instead of a problem, the system will retrieve the closest conditional and coordinated situations to the one containing the desired concept, which had been determined by the investigator. In this way, the student will understand how the concept was born in a decision-making process. For example, if the concept called “double skin façade” (*fachada de doble piel* in Spanish) is retrieved in the Telefonica office building, the explored graph will show the situations and links to KOs describing the reused building before intervention, the wind and shading analysis, the proposed bioclimatic strategies, and finally the particular façade related to the ventilated floor assembly and other components which are part of a global functional system. In this mode each alternative of every situation is displayed within each node, so the displayed graph contains only real chosen alternatives.

On the other hand, the second possible mode set as “*solución razonada*” is applicable to studio classes when the teacher wants to review an existing case and to simulate the mental process conducted by the designers. Thus, discussion and argumentation among students is produced in a Socratic Method: learning by debating and confronting different points of view.

In this mode every alternative is shown as a separate situation (node) rather than as a part of the previous situation. In this manner alternatives can be equally evaluated by the group to finally verify what alternative was really chosen and its justification.

Figure 9. Complete graph of one already uploaded case study in the SKOC tool.

On one hand, the first application mode set as “*solución real*” in the SKOC system is the voluntary search done by students. After the user has been given a design problem in class he goes to the search

For example, in the Telefonica office building case study the system will display situations such as the association of Telefonica with Telecom, the decisions about locating the offices in a building in the north of the city or reusing an existing building at the campus of Telecom, what particular existing buildings were analyzed in the campus to be reused, what the detected comfort and organization problems were, and what alternatives were analyzed to solve them, etc. Part of this decision-making process is shown in figure 10. The exploration ends when the graph is completely displayed and the designed building exposed, so a holistic understanding of the project is reached.

In any mode of the case explorer every new situation unfolds incrementally as the user progresses through the design process in a descending order. When the user drags the mouse over an already displayed situation a *tooltip* will present in a box its particular information and KOs. In this way, within a single page both the context (graph) and the definition of the situation are presented, along with direct links to particular KOs which are displayed at will in separate windows.

Likewise, the possibility of creating thematic classes is being considered so teachers may semantically organize their contents using the existing ontology and the case explorer in a reusable pedagogical format. Teachers will be able to easily link real

existing or new KOs and cases to contextualize the exposed lecture.

Finally, each case is qualitatively evaluated by researchers and teachers, so students can take into account these observations and include them in their case-based design.

CONCLUSIONS

When architecture students face a new design problem imposed by an exercise in a studio course, they heavily rely on referenced cases as an input to support their designs. However, the particular way of approaching cases is hindering creativity. As a result the Architecture Department at Uniandes has designed and partially developed a CBDA tool based on explanatory case studies. This tool uses precedent cases and acyclic graphs to explain the *dynamic situations* that produced a case in real context. Despite this tool is still under development, it is expected students will increase their analysis and design capacities by using it.

Even though this tool demands large amount of work when preparing and loading cases it is not seen as a problem. A single case can be re used every semester and for an undefined period of time until a better case is identified and solutions to a single problem are increased. Another benefit of SKOC is its capability to integrate knowledge from other courses to studios which do not happen traditionally, so this

Figure 10. Schematic initial decision-making process of the Telefonica office building case study.

contextualized knowledge can be taken into account when students formulate a new design.

CURRENT STATE AND FUTURE ACTIONS

The current state of SKOC can be seen from different perspectives: the case uploader and the case explorer platforms are already developed and three initial cases are available for students. The *tooltip* that shows the information of every situation is under development after some other alternatives were unsuccessfully tried. In the same way there are several actions which need to be done. These can be classified into three actions: expansion, experimentation and research (figure 11).

The first action is to analyze the possibility of creating a conceptual ontology to enable semantic integration of concepts, which is different from the existing on specific components currently contained in KOC. This will allow organizing not only component but concept knowledge and integrally feeding both types within the Architectural domain.

The second action is the verification of the initial objective of proposing a CBDA to support decision-making processes as a strategy to overcome design fixation patterns in architecture students. At this moment the first experiment with students is being prepared so future corrections can be done.

Finally, more explanatory case studies are already being developed dealing with similar problems to those presented in studio courses. Despite the tool has not been tested yet, this work is being done as in previous international conferences SKOC was presented, it was considered a novelty as it manages to store mental processes rather than just typified data.

In addition, some developed cases are being physically published such the book called "*Once upon a time: the Avianca office tower*" (*Erase una vez un edificio; torre de oficinas de Avianca* in Spanish).

Figure 11. Current state and future actions for SKOC.

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